

ilar set of varieties was sown 17 Jul 1982 and their performance was compared to that of the ratooned crop.

Plant height, panicle length, and tiller number were higher for ratoons than for

normal sown man rice. Ratooned Tillakachari and Achra 108/1 yielded more than the aman sowing of the same varieties (see table). The mean yield of ratooned rice varieties equaled that of

normal sown rice, indicating the suitability of ratoon cultivation in lowland areas where flood or sudden water stagnation hampers the freshly planted rice crop during the wet season. □

Fungi-caused rotten disease of azolla

Parkpian Arunyanart, Arunee Surin, Wanchai Rochanahasadin, and Somkid Disthaporn, Rice Pathology Branch, Division of Plant Pathology and Microbiology, Department of Agriculture, Bangkok, Bangkok 10900, Thailand

In 1981, the fungus *Myrothecium* sp. was discovered to cause rotten disease of azolla. In 1982 azolla propagation in north-east Thailand was increased and an outbreak of rotten disease occurred. Damage was more severe than in 1981 and symptoms were different from those caused by *Myrothecium* sp. Disease samples were collected from a farmer's propagation pond in Sakolnakorn Province in Nov-Dec 1982. Six genera of fungi were isolated: *Myrothecium* sp., *Rhizoctonia* sp., *Sclerotium* sp., *Fusarium* sp., and two unidentified fungi. One unidentified genus had a yellow colony of mycelium, the other a black colony. All were grown on potato dextrose agar.

Healthy azolla was individually inoculated with the six isolated fungi and grown in a 38-cm-diameter pot. Each

Comparison of disease symptom development on *Azolla pinnata* after inoculation by selected fungi.

Fungus	Symptom development, (days after inoculation)			Azolla death (days after inoculation)	Azolla rotting (days after inoculation)	Disease appearance
	Leaf	Stem	Root			
<i>Rhizoctonia</i> sp.	2	2	2	3-4	5-7	Infected fern turned pale-brown in color, then brown to dark brown.
<i>Myrothecium</i> sp.	2	2	3	3-5	10-15	Infected fern turned grey-green in color, then grey-brown to dark brown.
<i>Sclerotium</i> sp.	7	-	-	-	-	Infected fern showed only small brown lesion on leaf.
<i>Fusarium</i> sp.	-	-	-	-	-	No symptom
Unidentified (yellow colony)	-	-	-	-	-	No symptom
Unidentified (black colony)	-	-	-	-	-	No symptom
Distilled water (control)	-	-	-	-	-	No symptom

treatment and a distilled water sprayed control was replicated four times. Disease development was recorded.

Rhizoctonia sp. damaged azolla most, causing infected ferns to rot 5-7 days after inoculation. *Myrothecium* sp.

caused rotting 10-15 days after inoculation (see table). *Sclerotium* sp. caused small brown lesions on the leaves 7 days after inoculation, but did not cause rotting. *Fusarium* sp. and the two unidentified fungi did not cause the disease. □

Effects of plant population and urea supergranule deep placement on rice yield

G. S. Thangamuthu and S. Subramanian, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641-012, India

We studied the effect of plant population and deep placement of urea supergranules (USG) on rice yield at Coimbatore in 1980 wet season and 1981 dry season (Jan-May). The soil was clay loam with pH 7.8, 0.38% carbon, and CEC 26.8 meq/100 g.

The trial was laid out in a randomized block design with four planting treatments in five replications. Plot size was .0 × 4.0 m. Heavy tillering rice Co 43 from the cross Dhasal/IR20 was planted

Effect of plant spacing and USG placement on rice panicles and grain yield of Co 43.^a

Spacing (cm)	Hills (no./m ²)	USG (no./4 hills)	Panicles/m ²		Panicle wt (g)		Grain yield (t/ha)	
			WS	DS	WS	DS	WS	DS
15 × 10	66	1	489	476	1.90	1.85	4.9	6.1
15 × 20	33	2	315	586	2.68	2.44	5.2	6.6
22.5 × 20	22	3	233	495	2.85	2.22	5.2	6.3
30 × 20	16	4	225	470	2.39	2.24	5.1	6.2
CD (0.05)	-	-	39	30	0.27	0.48	0.2	0.2

^aUrea supergranule (USG) at 75 kg N/ha was deep placed. WS = wet season, DS = dry season.

at 2 seedlings/hill. The table gives treatment details and number of panicles, panicle weight, and grain yield.

Results indicated that 20 × 15 cm spacing (33 plants/m²), or half the population of conventional spacing, gave significantly higher grain yield in both

seasons. Yield with 22 plants/m² equaled that of 33 plants/m² during wet season. However, yield with 33 plants/m² was significantly higher than with 22 plants/m² during dry season (see table).

The number of panicles/m² was significantly higher in a conventional plant-